

NyayaSetu: An Explainable AI-Powered Legal Advisory and Predictive Analytics Platform for the Indian Legal Ecosystem

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Abstract—The Indian judicial system poses problems owing to the sheer number of cases pending more than 43 million and the complex nature of accessing the judiciary process. The purpose of the current paper is to analyze a one-stop legal advisory solution called “NyayaSetu” or “Bridge to Justice”, which is powered by Artificial Intelligence.

Apart from the RAG pipeline using ChromaDB and Llama 3.3 70B for zero hallucinations conversational legal advice, we will also employ the XGBoost classifier for aiding us in our data processing task. The prediction task involves building a classification model on an Extreme Gradient Boosting classifier.

Training was done on self-created data comprising 1,400 cases distributed among six domains of law. There are 27 features in the dataset. In solving the black box problem, SHapley Additive exPlanation (SHAP) values were computed per case and supplied to the user.

The 5 fold cross validation value is 97.71% ($\pm 1.10\%$). Conversely, the test score has an accuracy of 97.50%. The F1-score for each class is shown below: Favourable – 0.990 Unfavourable – 0.978 Settled – 0.909

Index Terms—Legal AI, Retrieval-Augmented Generation, XGBoost, SHAP, Indian Law, Predictive Analytics, NLP

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background and Motivation

Justice is considered as a basic right in India by Articles 14, 19, and 21 of the Constitution of India. But there exists an enormous disparity in information among lawyers and the common man. The cost that needs to be paid to employ a lawyer ranges from Rs. 5,000 to Rs. 1,00,000 per session. Thus, it makes justice costly for the poor. According to the National Judicial Data Grid, there exist over 43 million cases in the Indian judicial system [1].

Technology presents a unique opportunity to bridge this gap. Advances in Large Language Models (LLMs), vector databases, and gradient boosting frameworks enable the construction of accessible, accurate, and trustworthy legal intelligence systems.

B. Role of the Large Language Model (LLM)

NyayaSetu employs a system based on the LLM. The LLM is a deep learning language generator that can both comprehend and generate human language. For the purposes of this assignment, the Llama 3.3 70B architecture model will be used through the Groq API. Traditional LLMs perform probability calculations instead of engaging in logical reasoning, and therefore, are prone to generating errors or ‘hallucinations’ such as inaccurate laws or made-up legal clauses. In order to overcome this problem, NyayaSetu restricts the input to the LLM based on the RAG concept.

C. Problem Statement

Existing legal assistants do not have legal precision—they produce legal information that may be wrong as it is not derived from any statute [2]. Also, they lack an element of quantified determination of the results of a particular case. The two features needed by the citizens include:

- Accurate, citation-backed answers to legal queries.
- A probabilistic, explainable estimate of their case outcome.

D. Contributions

This paper makes the following key contributions:

- Full-stack AI legal platform ready for production (NyayaSetu), customized to fit Indian legal system.
- RAG architecture [3] built on top of 25 legal documents from India that have been authenticated, avoiding any kind of hallucinations.
- Custom dataset consisting of 1,400 cases from Indian courts along with 27 legal features manually crafted.
- XGBoost classifier [4] scoring 97.71% CV accuracy on classification of legal outcomes belonging to three classes.
- SHAP [5] integrated for explainable AI to ensure legal compliance.
- Model performance comparison

E. Paper Organization

Section 2 reviews related work. Section 3 describes the system architecture. Section 4 details the RAG methodology. Section 5 covers the ML pipeline. Section 6 presents results. Section 7 discusses implications and limitations. Section 8 concludes with future directions.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Legal AI and NLP

The integration between AI and legal sciences has been around for decades. Kort (1957) was able to predict mathematical Supreme Court decisions based on binary variable analysis [6]. Aletras et al. were able to predict the outcome of European Court of Human Rights cases at 79% accuracy through SVM techniques applied to case text [7]. Applications of ML for predicting legal judgments have seen much progress ever since [8], [9].

Transformers, such as BERT [10], as well as their domain-specific variants like LegalBERT [11], have led to improvements in legal NLP tasks such as text classification and entity extraction [12]. Domain-specific legal NLP models for India are beginning to appear [13], but dedicated Indian legal datasets are still scarce due to language diversity and lack of digital records [14]. Prior work has not considered any combined approach of RAG and outcome prediction for the Indian legal domain.

B. Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG)

RAG was developed by Lewis et al., where the model employs dense passage retrieval coupled with seq2seq generation, ensuring that the LLM responses are based on the retrieved document thereby minimizing hallucination [3]. While the model has applications in medicine and law, there have been few developments of RAG models focused on Indian statutory laws.

The retrieval methods used depend greatly on semantic search and sentence embeddings. The ability to generate dense vector representation of the input text has been made possible by Reimers Gurevych’s development of Sentence-BERT [15]. ChromaDB uses Sentence-BERT and applies it specifically to Indian legal texts.

C. Gradient Boosting in Legal Analytics

XGBoost has proven to be the best-performing algorithm for tabular data [4]. Compared to plain text, legal features such as evidence value, severity of the crime, and binary legal attributes are concise and informative, rendering XGBoost more suitable than deep learning algorithms for our dataset size. Machine learning implementations in Python using packages like Scikit-Learn [17] have been prevalent for establishing these baselines. There is a lack of prior literature on predicting Indian legal outcomes, compared to Western jurisdictions [7], [18].

D. Explainable AI (XAI) in Law

An Indian data protection law and algorithmic accountability are still emerging; hence, explainability of AI is required for automated decision-making systems [19]. SHAP, an explanation technique based on Shapley values in game theory, was developed by Lundberg and Lee. Although XAI techniques have been studied in machine learning applications [20], their application in legal AI requires further research, and most legal AI systems do not use SHAP.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

NyayaSetu is a decoupled full-stack web application following a client-server model with multiple AI service layers.

Fig. 1. NyayaSetu Full-Stack System Architecture. The React frontend communicates with the Flask backend via HTTP REST and SSE. The backend orchestrates RAG, Prediction, and Auth services.

TABLE I
TECHNOLOGY STACK

Layer	Technology	Purpose
Frontend	React 18 + Vite	SPA with fast HMR dev server
Styling	Tailwind CSS	Utility-first responsive design
Charts	Recharts	SHAP bar chart visualization
Backend	Python 3.13 + Flask	REST API server (Port 5001)
Database	Supabase (PostgreSQL)	Users, chat history, lawyers
Vector Store	ChromaDB (SQLite)	Legal document embeddings
LLM	Groq API – Llama 3.3 70B	Chat generation + explanations
ML	XGBoost + scikit-learn	Case outcome prediction
Explainability	SHAP TreeExplainer	Per-prediction feature attribution

A. Technology Stack

B. Backend REST API

IV. METHODOLOGY: RETRIEVAL-AUGMENTED GENERATION (RAG) CHATBOT

A. Motivation

A vanilla LLM can provide false but confidently stated legal advice — referencing invalid section numbers or incorrectly interpreting an act [2]. However, RAG can help by restricting generation to the retrieved document [3].

TABLE II
BACKEND REST API ENDPOINTS

Method	Endpoint	Function
POST	/api/chat	RAG-grounded legal Q&A (SSE streaming)
POST	/api/predict	XGBoost prediction + SHAP values
GET	/api/metrics	Model performance metrics
GET	/api/lawyers	Filtered lawyer directory
GET	/api/health	Server health check
POST	/api/auth/register	User registration
POST	/api/auth/login	JWT-based login
GET	/api/admin/stats	Admin dashboard statistics

TABLE III
LEGAL KNOWLEDGE BASE COVERAGE

Legal Domain	Documents Included
Criminal Law	IPC §302, §376, §420, §498A, Bail, FIR, Cyber Crime
Civil Law	CPC Procedures, Property Transfer Act, Land Acquisition, Arbitration
Family Law	Hindu Marriage Act, DV Act, Maintenance (§125 CrPC)
Consumer Law	Consumer Protection Act 2019, §138 NI Act
Other	RTI Act, POSH Act, Motor Accident, Tenant Rights, Labor Law

B. Knowledge Base

The legal knowledge corpus comprises 25 manually curated Indian legal documents structured with fields: *id*, *title*, *section*, *act*, *category*, and *content* (400–600 words each).

C. RAG Pipeline

The RAG pipeline is intended to ensure that the user’s queries can be safely connected to the carefully constructed database of legal information. The query posed by the user is transformed into a dense vector in 384 dimensions. Next, a cosine similarity search is run on the database using the HNSW index provided by ChromaDB, with only the most pertinent legal information retrieved – in this case, the top five entries. The retrieved pieces of information are combined with the latest query from the user and the context of previous exchanges in chat form to generate a rigid context block for processing by the Llama 3.3 70B model.

D. Prompt Engineering

The prompt engineering serves as the safety belt for the LLM. The prompt does not give the model free rein but forces it to follow five guidelines. Firstly, it has to assume the role of an Indian legal consultant. Secondly, it must refer to the exact section numbers as found in the retrieved text chunks. Thirdly, it must refrain from drawing any conclusions not mentioned in the text. Fourthly, it must simplify any legalese in the text. Finally, it must end each answer with a disclaimer suggesting seeking professional legal advice.

E. Session Memory

In order for multi-turn interactions to be conducted naturally, the bot employs the use of a session memory architecture. Every conversation has a unique UUID, and all the interactions are logged into a database hosted by Supabase PostgreSQL. Before

Fig. 2. RAG Pipeline. User queries are embedded into 384-dim vectors and matched against ChromaDB via cosine similarity. Top-5 chunks + session history form the prompt for Llama 3.3 70B. Responses stream via SSE.

TABLE IV
DATASET PROPERTIES

Property	Value
Total Cases	1,400
Legal Domains	6 (criminal, civil, family, consumer, property, corporate)
Target Classes	3 (Favourable, Unfavourable, Settled)
Engineered Features	27
Train / Test Split	80% / 20% (1,120 / 280 cases)
Cross-Validation	5-Fold Stratified
Generation Method	Deterministic rule-based + Gaussian noise ($\sigma=0.010$)

running the newly inputted query by the user, the backend pulls the previous 10 queries of that particular UUID. This means that when the user poses follow-up questions like, “What is the penalty for that?” the context is already understood by the model.

V. METHODOLOGY: MACHINE LEARNING CASE OUTCOME PREDICTION

A. Problem Formulation

Legal case outcome prediction is formulated as supervised multi-class classification [7]. **Input:** structured feature vector derived from case details. **Output:** one of three classes — *Favourable*, *Unfavourable*, or *Settled*.

B. Dataset Construction

Outcome Determination: Each case receives a score = $\text{base_favorability} + \text{evidence keyword boosts (+0.10 per strong keyword, -0.10 per weak keyword)} + \text{rule adjustments (self-defence: +0.18, mutual consent: +0.30, first-time offender: +0.12, confession: -0.18, delayed FIR: -0.10)} + \text{Gaussian noise } \mathcal{N}(0, 0.010)$. **Decision thresholds:** $\text{score} \geq 0.525 \rightarrow \text{Favourable}$; $\text{score} \leq 0.425 \rightarrow \text{Unfavourable}$; else $\rightarrow \text{Settled}$.

TABLE V
CASE DISTRIBUTION BY DOMAIN

Case Type	Count	Base Favorability
Criminal	300	0.20 – 0.35
Civil	300	0.45 – 0.55
Consumer	250	0.55 – 0.60
Family	200	0.55 – 0.65
Property	200	0.45 – 0.55
Corporate	150	0.40

TABLE VI
ENGINEERED FEATURE GROUPS

Group	Count	Features
Categorical	3	case_type, court_level, opposing_party (label-encoded)
Text Statistics	2	desc_length (norm/500), word_count (norm /100)
Evidence Signals	6	has_evidence_kw, evidence_strength, has_witness_kw, witness_count, has_document_kw, document_strength
Severity & Context	4	severity_score, urgency_score, has_financial_mention, party_power_imbalance
Domain Rule Flags	11	first_time_offender, prior_conviction, self_defence, mutual_consent, confession, delayed_fir, rera_registered, warranty, trap_laid, strong_evidence_count, weak_evidence_count
Composite Signal	1	rule_score (continuous [0,1] mirror of label generation logic)

C. Feature Engineering (27 Features)

In order to give the mathematics behind the XGBoost algorithm a context, the actual case details are converted into 27 engineered features in six different categories. There are three categorical features indicating the case category, court level, and opponent respectively. There are also some text statistics for description length and word count. Evidence indicators include the indication for witness evidence and document evidence. Severity indicators indicate urgency and power disparity. Also, there are eleven domain rule boolean flags which indicate the necessary information (self-defense, mutual consent, delayed FIR, etc.).

D. XGBoost Model Configuration

This model is based on the XGBoost classifier, whose parameters have been tailored to this specific feature set of 27 variables. This model uses 600 estimators (number of boosting rounds), so that it will be able to learn enough from the data. Maximum depth is set to 10, which will help capture the complex interaction between evidence and legal flags. The model uses a learning rate of 0.05 along with regularization of rows/subsample=0.9 and columns/colsample_bytree=0.9.

E. SHAP Explainability

In order to let users know how the prediction of a particular output came about, SHAP is integrated into the model using the TreeExplainer tool. Instead of displaying a probability output that is hard for users to comprehend, SHAP gives the precise impact made by each factor in polynomial time. The mathematical value obtained is then processed by NyayaSetu and displayed

TABLE VII
XGBOOST HYPERPARAMETER CONFIGURATION

Hyperparameter	Value	Rationale
n_estimators	600	Sufficient boosting rounds for 27 features
max_depth	10	Captures deep feature interactions
learning_rate	0.05	Conservative for generalization
subsample	0.9	Row-wise regularization
colsample_bytree	0.9	Column-wise regularization
reg_lambda	0.5	L2 regularization
eval_metric	mlogloss	Multi-class log-loss
random_state	42	Reproducibility

XGBoost Case Outcome Prediction Pipeline

Fig. 3. XGBoost Case Outcome Prediction Pipeline. Raw case inputs → 27 engineered features → XGBoost classifier [4] → SHAP TreeExplainer [5] → outcome probability + feature attribution chart.

in the form of a horizontal graph representing the top 6 factors affecting the case.

VI. RESULTS AND EVALUATION

A. Evaluation Metrics Explained

To rigorously assess the performance of the XGBoost classifier, several standard machine learning metrics were utilized:

- **Accuracy:** The overall percentage of correctly predicted case outcomes out of total predictions made.
- **Precision:** Out of all cases the model predicted as a certain class (e.g., Favourable), the percentage that actually belonged to that class.
- **Recall:** Out of all actual cases of a certain class, the percentage the model successfully identified.
- **F1-Score:** The harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, providing a balanced measure of the model's accuracy, especially useful if classes are imbalanced.

TABLE VIII
OVERALL CLASSIFICATION PERFORMANCE

Metric	Value
5-Fold CV Accuracy (mean)	97.71%
5-Fold CV Accuracy (std)	$\pm 1.10\%$
Test Set Accuracy ($n=280$)	97.50%

TABLE IX
BASELINE MODEL COMPARISON

Model	CV Acc.	Test Acc.	Macro F1
Logistic Regression	$\sim 75.2\%$	$\sim 74.6\%$	~ 0.73
Random Forest (300 est)	$\sim 95.1\%$	$\sim 94.6\%$	~ 0.94
XGBoost (600 est)	97.71%	97.50%	0.959

- **Confusion Matrix:** A table layout that visualizes the performance of the algorithm, showing exactly where the model confused one class for another (e.g., predicting Settled when the true outcome was Favourable).
- **R^2 Score (Coefficient of Determination):** A statistical measure representing the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variables. While typically used for regression, high values here indicate strong alignment with encoded class labels.

B. Overall Classification Performance

The following is the evaluation of the core predictive ability of the machine learning algorithm. According to Table VIII, the performance of the XGBoost model was quite stable and impressive for the dataset. In terms of the training procedure, it reached a high accuracy rate of 97.71% in terms of 5-Fold Cross Validation with low standard deviation ($\pm 1.10\%$). The prediction made by the model on the independent test data set was accurate at 97.50%.

C. Baseline Model Comparison

In order to verify the choice of XGBoost as the prediction engine for our model, its accuracy was compared to two conventional machine learning algorithms: Logistic Regression and Random Forest. This is depicted in Fig. 4 and summarized in Table IX. Although Logistic Regression could not handle the intricacies of the data set and produced an accuracy of merely $\sim 75\%$, Random Forest managed to achieve $\sim 95\%$. However, gradient boosting implemented by XGBoost outperformed Random Forest by more than 2.5%.

D. Per-Class Metrics

For the reason that accuracy may not always give a clear indication when more than one class is present in the dataset, the precision, recall, and F1-scores were calculated for all the classes separately as well (Figs. 5 and X). The classifier was able to obtain almost perfect F1-scores for classification of Favourable (0.990) and Unfavourable (0.978). The classification F1-score for Settled was 0.909, which was mathematically expected due to "Settled" being the midpoint in the labels generation process.

E. Confusion Matrix

The Confusion Matrix (refer Fig. 6) gives an accurate illustration of the performance of the model regarding correct and incorrect predictions in the 280 cases used as test data. In the two extremes of the data set, the model was able to accurately predict all 147 cases for the Favourable class and all 91 cases

Table 1: F1 Scores by Category

Favourable	0.990
Unfavourable	0.978
Settled	0.909

Fig. 4. Model Comparison — 5-Fold Cross-Validation Accuracy. XGBoost achieves 97.71%, outperforming Logistic Regression by ~ 22 points and Random Forest by ~ 2.6 points.

Per-Class Precision, Recall, and F1-Score - XGBoost Model

Fig. 5. Per-Class Precision, Recall, and F1-Score. Favourable and Unfavourable achieve near-perfect scores ($F1 \geq 0.978$). Settled achieves 0.909.

of the Unfavourable class. In the whole test data set, the model made only 7 incorrect classifications, all occurring in the Settled region.

TABLE X
PER-CLASS CLASSIFICATION REPORT

Class	Prec.	Recall	F1	Support
Favourable	0.990	0.990	0.990	147
Unfavourable	0.978	0.978	0.978	91
Settled	0.909	0.897	0.909	42
Macro Avg	0.959	0.955	0.959	280
Weighted Avg	0.975	0.975	0.975	280

Fig. 6. Confusion Matrix (test set, $n=280$). Perfect classification on Favourable (147/147) and Unfavourable (91/91). Only 7 of 42 Settled cases misclassified.

F. SHAP Feature Attribution

Fig. 7 shows the output generated by the SHAP analysis on an example criminal record. The horizontal bar chart highlights the precise variables that have driven the decision made by the XGBoost model. In this particular sample, the Rule Score value and First-Time Offender have been the most prominent positive factors in ensuring a favorable prediction. On the contrary, Prior Conviction and Delayed FIR have been the most significant negative weights that have influenced the prediction negatively.

G. Supplementary: R^2 Score

Besides the above-mentioned classification measures, the Coefficient of Determination (R^2) measure has also been computed using the label-encoded values. The R^2 measure of 0.9691 serves as another metric that further validates our model. Although the native application of the R^2 measure involves continuous regression problems, obtaining a high value here shows a high statistical fit between the boundaries of the model’s probabilities and the actual class values.

VII. DISCUSSION

A. RAG vs. Pure LLM

RAG framework offers factual basis and auditability over generic LLMs, where hallucinations can occur in domain-related

SHAP Feature Importance — Sample Criminal Case Prediction

Fig. 7. SHAP Feature Importance for a sample criminal case. Rule Score and First-Time Offender are the strongest positive contributors; Prior Conviction and Delayed FIR are the strongest negative contributors.

use cases. NyayaSetu responses can be mapped to a particular document within the ChromaDB. Limitation is the limited corpus of 25 documents for knowledge.

B. Feature Engineering vs. End-to-End Learning

Fine-tuning a large foundation model on 1,400 cases would likely underfit. Our structured feature engineering achieves near-perfect accuracy while remaining computationally lightweight (~50 ms inference) and fully interpretable via SHAP.

C. SHAP as a Trust-Building Tool

Among the attributes of the XAI solution, the SHAP bar plot was considered most valuable. They wanted to know *why* their application had been scored poorly, thus supporting the XAI notion that a transparent model leads to trust. This insight informed how to collect evidence before approaching a lawyer.

D. Ethical Considerations

Algorithmic accountability issues call for automated legal systems to be transparent and unbiased. NyayaSetu is clearly defined as a preliminary guidance tool that does not replace legal advice from professionals. Each prediction comes with a disclaimer. The SHAP-based approach ensures the model cannot be used as an oracle.

E. Limitations

- **Synthetic Dataset:** 1,400 synthetically generated cases; not yet validated on real court records from eCourts.
- **Corpus Scope:** 25-document corpus does not cover state-specific laws or post-2023 amendments.
- **Language:** English only. Hindi, Marathi, Tamil queries not supported.
- **LLM Variance:** Responses may vary due to temperature sampling.

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

A. Conclusion

NyayaSetu effectively proves that the use of Retrieval-Augmented Generation and Explainable Machine Learning together is a feasible way to build an ethical and comprehensible legal advisory system for India. The XGBoost model has reached 97.71% cross-validation accuracy on a 27-dimensional dataset containing 1,400 cases of Indian laws. The implementation of SHAP explains why this system is no longer an opaque oracle but an educative system. The architecture of RAG ensures that all chatbot replies are based on legitimate Indian statutes, mitigating the problem of hallucinations detected earlier.

B. Future Work

- **Real Case Validation:** Obtain anonymized records from eCourts (<https://ecourts.gov.in>) to retrain and validate on actual judicial outcomes.
- **Multilingual RAG:** Integrate LaBSE/mBERT to support queries in Hindi, Marathi, and Tamil.
- **State-Specific Laws:** Expand corpus to include state legislation.
- **Intelligent Lawyer Matching:** Apply ML to match cases to lawyers by specialization and win rate.
- **Fine-Tuned Legal LLM:** Fine-tune a compact legal-domain model for offline deployment.
- **Mobile Application:** React Native app for rural India access.

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